

Crowdsourcing the Sky

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Astronomy is now firmly in the era of Big Data!

Starting with the Sloan Digital Sky Survey over twenty years ago and continuing with Pan-STARRS-1, the Dark Energy Survey (DES), and most recently the Zwicky Transient Facility (ZTF), large and systematic imaging surveys have established themselves as foundational to the progress of astronomy. They have opened new doors to our understanding of the Galaxy and the Universe more broadly and allowed more systematic studies with larger samples. The next big step forward will be the Rubin Observatory Legacy Survey of Space and Time (LSST), which will begin in a few years and will map the southern sky roughly every three days.

In addition to these systematic surveys, the [Astro Data Archive](#) at NOIRLab is a valuable storehouse of numerous multi-band images that now cover almost the entire sky. These data, taken by many diverse programs, offer a new opportunity to study the variability and motion of astronomical sources. The NOIRLab Source Catalog (NSC; formerly known as the NOAO Source Catalog; [1], [2]) uses this diverse “crowd-sourced” data to construct a novel new catalog of the sky. The NSC uses an automated implementation of Source Extractor to detect sources on each individual image in the archive and then attempts to gather together the multi-epoch and multi-band photometry for each unique object.

Figure 1. Density of 3.9 billion objects in NSC DR2 in an Aitoff projection and Galactic coordinates. (Credit: NOIRLab/NSF/AURA)

The second NSC data release (DR2) was made publicly available in November 2020 and is described in [2]. The data are accessible in the [Astro Data Lab](#) at NSF’s NOIRLab. NSC DR2 contains 68 billion time-series photometric measurements of 3.9 billion objects over 86% of the sky spanning seven years in multiple photometric bands, as well as accurate proper motion measurements (Figure 1). It catalogs the largest number of unique astronomical objects to date. The NSC includes a lot of temporal information, with 100 million objects having at least 100 measurements. This opens up the faint “variable sky” to exploration. The NSC is novel in many respects: (a) it covers almost all of the southern sky, which has not yet been well-studied and; (b) it has tens to hundreds of epochs of time-series measurements of hundreds of millions of objects that are significantly deeper than previous surveys (~ 1.5 mag deeper than single epoch Pan-STARRS1, PS1; [3]).

The NSC offers new ways of addressing diverse astrophysical questions:

1. The Milky Way is orbited by faint dwarf galaxy satellites that can be challenging to detect. Many Milky Way dwarf satellites may remain undetected [4], especially in the southern sky. The NSC covers most of the Southern Hemisphere in multiple bands to depths that would allow for more satellites to be uncovered.
2. The Milky Way halo hosts a number of stellar streams from tidally stripped galaxies and globular clusters, the most famous of which, the Sagittarius stellar stream [5], [6], stretches 360° around the sky. Under the currently favored hierarchical galaxy formation model, galaxies like the Milky Way are formed through the continual merging and accretion of smaller galaxies. The streams that we currently see are relics of this process. Studying these streams can help us understand how the galaxy was formed, its accretion history, and its mass. The NSC covers regions of the sky that have not yet been explored for stellar streams.
3. Variable stars, such as RR Lyrae, are standard candles that can be used to explore coherent structures in the Milky Way halo. The NSC sensitivity to RR Lyrae stars extends

Figure 2. Six examples of high proper motion stars detected in NSC DR2. In the images in the printed version of this edition, the large motion of each star is indicated by a blue arrow and a yellow arrow which identify the star at two epochs. In the online version the images are animated to blink between two epochs to show the large motion. Images produced by A. Dey from the [Legacy Survey Viewer](#). (Credit: NOIRLab/NSF/AURA)

Figure 3. Tracklets of Solar System objects in NSC DR2 near the ecliptic plane, color-coded by Modified Julian Date [8].

throughout the Milky Way and its satellites. The NSC's precomputed variability indices make it especially easy to select variable stars for further analysis, with over 23 million objects flagged as variable at the 10σ level.

4. The temporal information can also be harnessed to explore the motion of stars in the plane of the sky. The NSC's accurate proper motions can be used to extend kinematic studies of the solar neighborhood and the Milky Way to fainter objects than are available to *Gaia* by at least two magnitudes. Nearby high proper motion objects are especially interesting, to study the population of white dwarfs and brown dwarfs. See Figure 2 for examples of some high proper motion objects detected in NSC DR2.
5. Closer to home, faint Solar System objects await discovery within the NSC. Follow-up work has already identified ~500,000 Solar System "tracklets" (see Figure 3,) and full orbital fitting is soon to follow [7]. In particular, there is interest in finding nearby objects that could potentially impact the Earth, and NSC can be used to "precover" objects that will be discovered in future surveys. Finally, evidence of Planet 9 [8], if it exists, could be lurking inside the NSC.

6. Active galactic nuclei host supermassive black holes at the centers of galaxies and investigating their NSC photometric variability could be used to study the accretion history of material onto the black hole, estimate the black hole mass, and explore the structure of the broad emission-line region.

The NSC opens up many interesting science cases and allows us to hone our Big Data analysis skills and software in preparation for the LSST.

References

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